

LINGUODIDACTIC, PSYCHOLINGUISTIC AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

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Abstract. In non-philological (construction) faculties, teachers face a number of problems when organizing the process of teaching English. As problems, we can see the high level of student interest in the subject, the organization of the connection of the studied language with professional skills, the integration of various disciplines and the organization of training sessions. The high quality of foreign language learning contributes to the competitiveness and professional mobility of the future specialist in the field of professional activity and communication. The following article discusses the linguodidactic, psycholinguistic and methodological aspects of teaching English in the construction and engineering disciplines.

Keywords : linguodidactics, psycholinguistics, integration, linguistics, research mechanism, communicative competence, gesture

Introduction . We have repeatedly written in our scientific articles that during the professional activity of a teacher, he should know not only the English language and methods of teaching it, but also the specific characteristics of a specialist. Teaching English oriented to the specialty, selecting exercises in English using the appropriate terminology used in practice, and organizing the sequence of integration of speaking, writing, reading, listening skills requires a lot of hard work. [48.155 Isroilova DM Organization and implementation of the "Special course" for training in a professional oriented language in the master's department. //Eastern European Scientific Journal. –Germany, 2018.–No.6.–S.155-161(13.00.02 No. 1)].

It was determined that in the construction areas it is necessary to consider the issues of linguodidactyly, taking into account the above issues. As is known, linguodidactyly is a general theory of language teaching. It studies the didactic goals, tasks and general laws of language teaching, depending on the nature of the material being studied, the specific features of the content, methods and means of teaching a particular language. According to D.V. Bulatova, linguodidactyly is a didactic section that is the methodological basis of the theory of teaching foreign languages [28.81 Bulatova DV Teoreticheskie osnovi kursa obucheniya inostrannomu yaziku v neyazikovom vuze. Author. diss.d.ped.nauk.– Moscow.–1999.–S.48 Electronic resource:<https://www.science-education.ru/ru/article/view?id> (data

obrasheniya: 02.12.2017)]. Based on the above issues, we have concluded that we need to improve foreign language teaching methods, taking into account regional requirements, professional needs, and social order.

Literature analysis. The scientific work of our scientists and foreign specialists and scholars on the linguodidactic, psycholinguistic and methodological aspects of teaching English in civil engineering disciplines and their application in the educational process was studied and analyzed in depth. Many PhD dissertations were studied, such as the dissertation of Palina Khakimjonovna Botirova "Linguodidactic foundations of developing students' coherent speech in English lessons" (on the example of technical students), and Toshmatov Alimardon Sotvoldievich "Technology for improving the speech competence of future foreign language teachers" (on the example of teaching written speech). Also, the scientific research of scientists such as JJ Jalolov, O'H. Hoshimov, LT Akhmedova, who conducted scientific research on the issues of teaching a foreign language in our Republic, were studied and analyzed. Foreign scientists: The following article, which represents (a certain part of) our research, was presented based on the study of books and studies by I.A. Borisov, D. Biriton, E.A. Semenova, and many other scientists.

Research methodology. Considering that teaching in civil engineering has its own characteristics, when choosing the content of teaching, the teacher should not only rely on the interaction of English with other subjects, but also take into account the relationship between the subjects, as this plays an important role in the preparation of educational material.

Linguodidactyly and methodology are not interconnected theoretically and practically. In his work, FM Litvinko, while studying the general laws of linguodidactyly, the functioning of foreign language communication mechanisms and methods of their formation, determined that the object of linguodidactyly is actually the process of language learning, and the theoretical justification of its research is the concepts, principles, content of language education, organizational forms of education, research mechanisms and the construction of the educational process. FM Litvinko emphasizes that the subject of linguodidactyly is language teaching (in the activities of the teacher), theoretical substantiation and understanding of the laws of interaction between teaching (in the activities of students), the principles of selecting the content of educational material and the technology of personalized knowledge acquisition. Linguodidactyly studies the laws of mastering any language, regardless of whether it performs the first or second task [56.2-3 Litvinko FM Linguodidactyly educational and methodological materials on educational disciplines for a specialist magistracy. 1-21 81 05 Innovations in language training. Electronic resource: <http://philology.bsu.by> (access date 6.11.2018)].

If we study the research work of our scientists, such as M. Zhusupov, we can see that linguodidactyly and methodology are defined differently: "Linguodidactyly deals with the creation of theoretical foundations of language teaching, that is, it describes the purpose of teaching and the theory of language, taking into account the linguistic and specific features of the educational process, which is engaged in the implementation of the results of linguodidactyly research in the methodology" [42.17-23 Zhusupov M. Linguodidactyly and methodology in the polyscientific system of language education// Russian language abroad. No. 2.-Moscow, 2009.-S.17-23.].

During his research, A.K. Krupchenko came to the conclusion that behind the concept of professional linguistic didactics there are methodologies (in the field of research,

management and modeling), teaching foreign languages oriented to the student's specialty, communicative competence aimed at forming a foreign language, a new section describing the linguistic aspects of the specialist [50.310Krupchenko A.K. Vvedenie v professionalnuyu lingvodidaktiku monograph.–Moscow MFTI, 2005. – P.310.]. Because, at present, there is a need to take into account certain laws in the training of personnel in the field of linguistic didactics.

The issue of taking into account linguodidactych when choosing the content of language teaching in technical faculties is considered. According to AK Krupchenko, linguodidactych arose from the objective social need of millions of engineers, scientists and representatives of other professions around the world to master a foreign language as a means of international professional information and experience exchange. In the process of training qualified specialists, modern approaches are required, especially in non-philological (construction) faculties, to develop theoretical and practical skills in teaching a foreign language.

A number of researchers, such as GI Bogin, ABBushev, ND Galskova, MA Bovtenko, RK Minyar-Beloruhev, and AS Markosyan, have scientifically proven the above issues in linguistic didactics, and the study of linguistic didactics includes the following laws:

- study the emergence of professional language didactics;
- develop a system of specific principles of professional language didactics;
- to achieve the goals of teaching future specialists the language;
- study the content of teaching foreign languages focused on a specific profession;
- be able to correctly choose the method and form of teaching to develop the language skills of a qualified specialist;
- Integrate foreign language and subject-related subjects when selecting and developing teaching aids, including textbooks, manuals, equipment, and technical teaching aids;
- formation of professional competence of a foreign language teacher for professionally oriented teaching [33.81 Galskova ND, Gez NI Theory of training in foreign languages. Linguistic teaching and methods: teaching. posobie dlya stud. lingv. un-tov i fak.in. yaz. vissh. ped. teaching. zavedeniy 3-e izd., ster.– Moscow, 2006.–P.81.].

The main task of professional linguistic didactics in the process of teaching foreign languages is to form a solid mastery of the language of the specialist. The specific principles of linguistic didactics of teaching languages to students can be considered as its basic laws. They include not only general didactic, but also target principles of linguistic didactics . These principles can also be considered as integrative, functional, problematic, multifaceted, communicative principles. For the first time, in relation to these principles, AK Krupchenko and AN Kuznesov developed the principle of selectivity, that is, the principle of selecting optimal ones from various problems, tasks, situations, forms and methods of professional education, in order to create an individual trajectory for the development of the personality of a specialist in the space of foreign language education [50.28 Krupchenko AK Vvedenie v professionalnuyu lingvodidaktiku monograph.–Moscow MFTI, 2005. – P.310.].

of globalization and the development of innovative technologies, the principle of harmonization of national and international standards has become increasingly relevant. This has also affected the conditions and means of implementing the principle of internationalization, which affects the profiling of education and foreign languages in

Uzbekistan. Possession of communicative competence in a foreign language allows a specialist to participate in international programs, as well as to become a competitive person in the international labor market.

AA Leontev, AN Leontev, IA Zimnyaya, RM Frumkin and many other scientists studied the issue of vocational orientation of students in the process of their research. As DL Matukhina notes, "Vocational orientation education is based on taking into account the needs of students in learning a foreign language, determined by the specifics of the future profession or specialty, which in turn requires learning a language" [61.35 Matukhina DL Osobennosti obucheniya inoyazichnomu obsheniyu studentov nelingvisticheskikh spetsialnostey na osnove kommunikativnogo podkhoda.– Tomsk, 2011.–S.35.].

R.M Frumkina considers the following important factor - the situation, which cannot be excluded not only from speech, but also from language, but also from the human factor [95.19 Frumkina RM Psycholinguistics.– Moscow, 2001.–P.19.] When organizing the educational process, the teacher should create practical tasks and exercises for the development of professional speech activity, taking into account various situations. During classes, the consolidation of skills, the selection of special exercises in a sequence from simple to complex, has a positive effect on the atmosphere in the classroom.

Another key factor is social demand. There are certain problems that need to be solved between the specialists of society who know the foreign language and use it in their professional activities, and the current practice of teaching foreign languages in non-philological faculties. One of these problems is the psycholinguistic features of professionally oriented English teaching.

According to A.N. Leontiev, it is "a science that studies the processes of speech formation, as well as the perception and formation of speech, their interaction with the language system. Therefore, the object of psycholinguistics, and linguistics in general, is the language and speech of a person used by him for various purposes and in various situations. It considers not the device of the sign system, but the process of creating and perceiving language signs in the minds of speakers of their native language" [58.19-42 Leontiev A.N. Problemi razvitiya psihiki. 4th ed. MGU–Moscow, 1981.– S.338.]. Psycholinguistics studies disorders in the speech process, as well as mental processes that occur during reading, listening, and mastering speech in our native language or in the language being studied.

The growing need to improve the quality of specialists who know foreign languages requires a complete revision of the psycholinguistic aspects of the content of English language teaching in technical universities. In our opinion, to solve these problems, it is necessary to take into account the needs of students and stimulate their demands by introducing modern teaching methods based on standards. This will serve as a basis for improving their professional level, taking into account the age characteristics of students, their level of knowledge, interest and desire to learn English.

DA Starkova and TV Polshe emphasize that in order to improve the effectiveness of teaching, it is necessary to take into account the following characteristics of students: a conscious attitude to the learning process, the need for freedom, motivation, practical orientation, the presence of life experience and professional training process and time factors [86.2-3 Starkova DA, Polshina TV Psycholinguistic features of teaching adults to a foreign language.– Ekaterinburg, 2010.–S.2-3.].

Analysis and results. The most important psycholinguistic features of teaching a foreign language to students are the use of individual teaching strategies, which include taking into account the difficulties encountered in the learning process, the implementation of the basic principles of its mastery. In accordance with modern requirements, graduates of higher education must be able to manage a system of universal human values, as well as have socio-cultural and intercultural communication skills that ensure an equal balance of social and professional relations. Speech activity is considered, from the point of view of psycholinguists, as a complex and important cognitive process of processing language information.

In modern psycholinguistics, several models of speech formation and perception have been developed. For example, AA Akishina and OE Kogon distinguished the following stages in the process of speech formation:

Motive, purpose, discourse complex, discourse, the ultimate goal of discourse.

At the same time, they divided cognitive processes into two subgroups:

Group 1 - real mental processes: memory, imagination, attention, thinking.

Group 2 - modeling, that is, establishing connections and relationships between objects, their transformation [15.39 Akishina AA, Kagan OE Vvedenie v psikolingvistiku. Moscow, 1999.–P.26-128.].

In order to organize an effective process of teaching students speech communication in a foreign language, it is necessary to consider the cognitive processes involved in speech production and take into account the main psycholinguistic features of speech communication. Memory, or rather memorization, is the most important mental process. Many psycholinguists have argued about this. They say that “At present, the most complex mental process is the memorization (imprinting), storage and subsequent repetition of new experiences” [15. 128 Akishina AA, Kagan OE Vvedenie v psikolingvistiku. Moscow, 1999.–P.26-128.].

To strengthen memory, in our opinion, the use of visual materials and appropriate technical teaching aids is very effective . It is very important to use situational exercises in practical English lessons to develop speaking skills. To do this, the exercises to be presented should consist of educational-speech and problem situations. The main idea of problem situations is to identify the problem that prevents students from understanding and solving the task, taking into account the updating of the content of the topics covered.

Our ideas about the psycholinguistic aspects of teaching English to students of non-philological educational institutions (in our case, construction faculties) are based on the views of many researchers, primarily A. N. Leontiev, who formulated the general principles of the process of mastering a foreign language: communicative, personal, cognitive.

By the communicative principle, we understand the process of interaction between people in communication. The cognitive principle is the acquisition of language in the process of creating and perceiving speech. The personal principle is responsible for the transfer of skills and abilities acquired in the learning process to real communication, taking into account the individual strategies and styles of students and their interests [58.338 Leontev A. N. Problems of psychological development. 4th ed. MGU–Moscow, 1981.–S.338.].

All of the above should be taken into account when forming a stable motivation of students in learning a foreign language, which is one of the most important psychological factors of success in mastering a foreign language. Motivation can have a positive effect on

existing shortcomings in education, even methodologically [58.123 Leontev AN Problemi razvitiya psihiki. 4th ed. MGU–Moscow, 1981.– S.338.]. These aspects allow us to learn to take into account the psychological characteristics and factors of students in the educational process.

Many scientists, such as A. A. Mirolyubov, E. V. Dubrovskaya, N. I. Gez, S. F. Shatilov, S. K. Folomkina and E. N. Solovova, in their research, emphasize that three components - linguistic, psychological and methodological - play an important role in the content of teaching foreign languages. Above, in our work, we examined the linguistic and psychological features of teaching English at non-philological (technical) faculties, in particular, at construction faculties. Now we can turn to the methodology to express our opinions on the methodological foundations of teaching English for professional purposes.

There are various methodological approaches to explaining the essence of education. According to VA Buxbinder, exercises are divided into three types: informational, operational and motivational . At the first stage, exercises ensure understanding and assimilation of the material by integrating the necessary information. At the second stage, tasks are developed using the necessary materials. At the third stage, speaking skills are improved [31.3 Buxbinder VA, Berman IM Situativnost i obuchenie ustnoy rechi/ № 5 Inostrannie yaziki v shkole. – Moscow, 1994.–P.27.].

When designing the teaching content, we proposed dividing the textbook into three main parts: lexical topics, grammatical skills, and phonetic exercises. In the lexical part, we selected a text related to the specialty and provided the necessary new words and phrases below. For example, “ *Construction Drawings: Content, Naming and marking*” Text on the topic (Construction drawings: content, name and marking). Familiarization with the text, necessary words and phrases: landscape, landscaping, landscape design, landscape architecture).

Loading, resisting, moving compensation-to compensate, turning, adjacent archesconstruction equipment, hanging hatch, column space, circuit diagram (CD), collar, engineering copier, fragile, frame, frame lug, fray, frayed insulationfrequency/voltage/phase, front etc.

In the grammatical part of the lesson, in our opinion, it is reasonable to use, compare, and study nouns and adjectives and their types in English, since grammar by its nature depends on the text, that is, the lexical part of the lesson. Students of the Civil Engineering Department of the Technical University can familiarize themselves with the types of drawings in English, use nouns and adjectives, and make suggestions on this topic. For example : Construction drawings are essential documents used in the construction industry to communicate the design and specifications of a building or infrastructure project. They are created by architects, engineers, and designers to provide detailed instructions for contractors, subcontractors, and workers to follow during construction. Construction drawings serve as the primary tool for construction, ensuring that the project is built according to the design intent, regulatory requirements, and safety standards. In such cases, we can introduce the importance of the relationship between lexis and grammar .

For phonetic practice, we have [t], [d] and [id]. We select a sound and develop the student's hearing ability by listening to various words and phrases with these sounds and help them try to pronounce this sound correctly when reading and speaking: For example, the following words: landscape, landscaping, landscape design, landscape architecture, turning, loading, circuit diagram, etc. By organizing this type of lesson, first of all, we can combine all

the skills of speaking, reading, and writing of students of the technical (construction) faculty, enriching their vocabulary with the necessary professional words and terms and forming their ability to express their thoughts grammatically correctly.

Uzbek scientists have developed a state educational standard for the system of continuous education in foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account some provisions of the Council of Europe document "Pan-European Competences in Knowledge of Foreign Languages". This means that from 05/08/2013, the system of "studying, teaching, assessing" any non-native language will reflect the approaches of various modern educational stages and levels of education in different conditions [12 Postanovlenie Kabineta Ministrov Respubliki Uzbekistan Obutverzhdenii Gosudarstvennogo obrazovatel'nogo standarta po inostrannimiyazikam sistemi neprerivnogo obrazovaniya].

If we continue in this system, taking into account all these criteria, we will be able to train specialists who meet modern requirements, as well as prepare them for internationally developed exams in English. It is known that it is important for our graduates to meet the requirements of modern education in the future. In our opinion, if we can properly organize the teaching of English with such a method, we can achieve satisfactory results.

In our opinion, the implementation of practical tasks and exercises helps to perceive the properties and signs of the phenomena being studied. At the same time, the process of engaging the student in cognitive activity occurs. As a result, the student begins to think freely, having accumulated a certain number of ideas in his mind. Understanding is the result of perceiving a certain amount of information, and this method of developing a skill is usually called "learning by doing". We can note that the above example is directly useful for mastering interdisciplinary connections and professional skills in the process of learning English.

It helps to improve the practical application of English language learning for professional purposes by preparing the necessary methodological materials.

While linguistic competence is focused on the phonetic, lexical, and grammatical materials of the language, communicative competence encompasses all types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading, writing).

[Inoyazichnaya kompetentnost' godnaya stanovitsya neot'emlemoy chastyu obshey professionalnoy kompetentnosti tekhnicheskogo spetsialista, poskolku pozvolyaet rasshirit vozmozhnosti access to new professional information and foreign languages, povisit profesionalnie znaniya i umeniya v ramkax svoey spetsialnosti i temimnogo predostavlyayet budushim vipuschnikam vozmozhnosti bolee peshesh tradustroystva].

Studying foreign language competence is today becoming an integral part of the general professional competence of future specialists in technical faculties, as it allows them to master the latest professional information in foreign languages, improve professional knowledge and skills in their specialty, and creates opportunities for graduates to successfully find employment.

If we turn to the views of LG Medvedeva in studying the methodological analysis of the English language aimed at professional competence, then the role of integration in the study of the language being studied in order to strengthen professional knowledge and form the professional qualities of the individual is considered great [68.1-5 Medvedeva LG Formirovanie inoyazichnogo professionalnoy orientirovannogo tezaurusu u studentov yuridicheskoy spetsialnosti. Izdvo Tom. un-ta Tomsk, 2010.-P.130.]. According to the data, the importance of integration is associated with interdisciplinary connections that arise in the

educational process, which create additional opportunities for the implementation of the goals of a foreign language as a means of forming professional competencies and enriching professional knowledge. In addition, according to a number of researchers, the current direction of educational activities in technical educational institutions of “teaching a specialty through language, teaching a language through a specialty” significantly increases the motivation level of students who are clearly aware of the practical benefits of the knowledge gained for their future successful professional activity [27.12 Burmistrova VA, Svich NA Model professionally oriented training of foreign language students of mining specialties. Saint Petersburg.-2010.-P.4. Electronic resource: http://group-lobal.org/ru/publication-professionalno-orientirovannogo_training_inostrannomu-yazyku-tudentov (from dostupa 21.01.2017)].

I would especially like to emphasize the importance of the “Construction Terminology” electronic educational dictionary, developed by us, which promotes activity and is aimed at attracting students to the English language and independent study of the language in the learning process. In our opinion, independent and individual mastery of knowledge helps to develop the necessary skills in various professional situations and when demonstrating skills. For example, if at the end of each lesson, under the theme *It is interesting to know!*, information about the profession that the student should acquire is provided, the development of general concepts and ideas about a special subject in the student’s mind will be significantly accelerated.

Students' independent work on the proposed tasks should be carried out in several stages:

- a) define the task;
- b) collect the necessary information;
- c) to discuss the issue at hand;
- g) develop a plan for the topic and implement it;

d) analysis of results [51.117 Kotelnikova E.Yu., Shportko IA Iz opita obucheniya inostrannomu yaziku dlya professionalnix seley v tekhnicheskome vuze. Perm, 2016-S.113-119.].

Conclusions and suggestions. Based on the data studied, we can say that the definition of problems develops critical thinking of students. They always focus on different situations in the learning process. Existing problems encourage students to collect information on specific issues and try to solve them. As a result, students gradually begin to put forward their hypotheses and discuss these issues, developing their communicative competence.

Thus, TD Margaryan emphasizes that he sees the principle of professional communicative orientation and the principle of professional intercultural orientation as the main methodological principles of teaching a foreign language in non-philological faculties (construction and engineering). In his opinion, the essence of the principle of professional communicative orientation is that “Foreign language” should be an integral part of the general professional training of a specialist, based on systematically involving students in oral (speaking, listening) and written (reading, writing) professional communication during their studies [62-188 Margaryan TD, Gurova GG, Alyavdina NG Professionally oriented training of the English language using information and communication technologies in a technical university.// Issues of modern science and practice. No. 3 (57).- Moscow- 2015. P.188- 195.].

Of course, the topic should be oriented to the latest achievements and reflect the professional interests of students, scientific progress in areas that provide them with opportunities for professional growth. Based on these words, we would like to propose another method. We consider the *KWL table*, developed by Donna Ogle in 1986, to be an effective method for organizing lessons. In the process of teaching professional English at the technical faculty (civil engineering), the Know, Want to Know, Learned method is very useful when working on a new topic, because it is based on the interests and needs of students. For example, we introduce a new topic to our students, such as “Construction drawing and marking”. First, we put a three-column table on the board and asked students to write in the first column what they know about the subject “Drawing” and its relationship with other subjects.

Table 1 “*KWL*” (table created by Donna Ogle in 1986).

Know (I know)	Want to know	Learn (I learn)
Information that students know	Information that students want to know	Information received by students at the end of the lesson.

Students write down what they know about it, then fill in the second column with what they want to know about construction drawings and types, markings, and how it relates to other components.

After the students have analyzed all the answers, the teacher explains this material by distributing the texts. During the reading process, students learn new words, answer the questions at the end of the text, and work according to Scheme 1.

1. Why is Physics so important for builders?
2. Do you really need drawing science as a constructor?
3. Why do building makers need Mechanical Drawing?
4. Does a builder need to have strong Math skills?

At the end of the task, students fill in the third and last column (*Learned*) with what they have learned. At the same time, students can add any new questions on this topic. It is during this process that the English teacher can check (write) the students' written speech, the grammatical structure of sentences and the correctness of phrases, as well as the correct use of words. In our opinion, *the KWL* table helps to develop not only reading skills, but also writing and speaking. The table presented above can be in different forms, since some information can be added to it and removed from it. In this case, we can add audio materials to develop students' auditory speech activity.

In the process of organizing lessons, not only language learning and teaching, but also student assessment should not be left out. A fair assessment by a teacher can motivate students and significantly affect the situation in the lesson. With the development of innovative types of teaching, types of assessment of student knowledge are also becoming more active. In our opinion, a rubric is a unique tool that helps to assess the quality of students' answers. It is often presented in a spreadsheet format and can be used by both teachers and students to activate and improve their work [49.258 Isroilova DM Rubric - one of the methods of indicative assessment of students' knowledge. // International Scientific-Practical Conference “Tendencies and Perspectives of the Development of Science and

Education in the Conditions of Globalization". –Ukraine, 2018. –P.258-261.]. There are a number of advantages of assessment using **a rubric , for example:**

- the quality of students' work is improved by knowing grades directly;
- self-analysis and self-esteem increase;
- positive cooperation is established between teacher and student during the learning process.

During collaboration with English teachers from other countries and distance training, issues of assessment using different types **of rubrics** were considered. The main ones are: integral heading

(Holistic), analytical (Analytic) and "target point" (Single-point) headings. Then these assessment methods were used in non-philological, in particular, construction faculties during research activities. A positive trend was established in the results of using headings, as it provides a clear connection between students and the teacher.

Undoubtedly, from the teacher's point of view, rubrics are a convenient tool for assessing students' group work, since they speed up and simplify the assessment process, and on the other hand, they increase the objectivity of monitoring students' knowledge. From the students' point of view, the use of rubrics ensures a clear understanding of the purpose and essence of the task, gives them clear instructions, and increases motivation. In addition, rubrics with the help of which students can independently assess their work and be guided to the highest level of task performance [49.261 Isroilova DM Rubric – one of the methods of indicative assessment of students' knowledge. // International Scientific and Practical Conference "Tendencies and Perspectives of the Development of Science and Education in the Conditions of Globalization". –Ukraine, 2018. –P.258-261.]. The above assessment methods have been widely discussed at international conferences and published in scientific journals.

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